

Stakeholders' awareness and acceptance of the vision, mission, goals, and outcomes statements of a teacher education college

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the awareness and acceptance of the stakeholders of a teacher education college in the Philippines of their university vision and mission and the college goals, and outcomes statements (VMGOs). Of the 700 target respondents, 406 stakeholders responded to the survey transcribed in Google Form. They were 42 school personnel, 106 parents, and 258 students; 301 females and 105 males. The five-point rating scales asked the respondents to assess their awareness and acceptance of 16 statements including one vision, one mission, five institutional outcomes (IO), two college goals, and seven program outcomes (PO). The respondents as a whole indicated they were very aware of the VMGOs and these were very acceptable for them. However, the school personnel were consistently more aware than the students and the parents/officials; while the parents/officials consistently indicated the lowest awareness and acceptability scores for all the statements. The results further revealed a significant acceptable relationship between awareness and acceptability scores. The variables share a variance ranging from 51% to 61% confirming that as awareness increases, acceptance rate also increases. Various implications of these findings are discussed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, external accrediting bodies focus on outputs as bases in judging the quality of a system [1]. Many countries like the United States, Canada, New Zealand [2], Hong Kong [3], and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) member-states [4] adopt an educational approach called outcomes-based education (OBE). In the Philippines, with Commission on Higher Education (CHED) memorandum 46 series of 2012, the implementation of this education became the main thrust of all higher education institutions [5]. All institutions have changed their statements of vision, mission, goals and objectives (VMGOs) into ones that can be translated into realities such that their students can attain them as they exit their courses.

The Isabela State University's vision and mission and its different curricular programs' goals and objectives serve as the guiding principles of Roxas Campus in serving the community through instruction, research, extension, and resource-generation. The vision, mission, goals, and objectives are the fundamental guides for the future of the institution and its academic programs. The vision should reflect what the university hopes to become in the future while the mission should express the broad procedures the university would undertake to fulfill its vision. The goals of the college, on the other hand, should direct the college toward the attainment of the university vision and long-term outcomes; and the program outcomes (PO)

should clearly establish the significant and complex competencies educators want their students to be able to do successfully before they can get the degree.

The university conducted the first leg of strategic development planning in 2017, and included in the planning sessions is the revision of the vision and mission of the university. The 2019-2024 strategic development plan, where the new university vision and mission are stipulated, had been institutionalized by Virtue of Board of Regents (BOR) resolution No. 16, s. 2019. The vision of the university is to be a leading research university in the ASEAN region, and its mission is to be committed to developing globally competitive human, technological resources and services through quality instruction, innovative research, responsive community engagement and viable resource management programs for inclusive growth and sustainable development. The desired institutional outcomes (IO) are graduates who are communicators, inquiry-focused and knowledgeable, competitive, collaborative and effective leaders, and lifelong learners.

The goals of the teacher education college are to: i) enhance the qualification of educators for academic and professional development equipped with training and educational innovation as well as research and extension; and ii) prepare and develop highly qualified education teachers and skilled technologists through and well-rounded pre-service trainings in both academic and vocational fields for diverse community of learners. Lastly, the PO are teachers who: i) possess wide range of theoretical and practical skills of an effective delivery instruction; ii) can perform the necessary competencies needed in the different learning areas in the secondary school; iii) can conduct research of instruction; iv) can undertake actual training in community development through extension activities; v) can apply appropriate innovative and alternative teaching approaches; vi) can practice the professional and ethical requirements of the teaching profession; and vii) can demonstrate desirable Filipino value as a foundation for social citizenship participation.

Since the university has a newly approved vision and mission statement (Isabela State University strategic plan 2019), stakeholders are mandated to actively disseminate, implement, and realize what the university wanted to become in the future. The VMGOs, which are the desires of the university, must be the ultimate focus of the curricula and policies and they must be clear to all stakeholders most especially the teachers and the students [6]–[10]. Moreover, research by Biggs and Tang [11] added that high competence is only facilitated when all individuals involved in the educational arena accept and are aware of their statements of qualities (e.g. VMGOs). Hence, the attainment of these statements largely depends on the extent of acceptance and awareness of the stakeholders.

The stakeholders' awareness and acceptability of the statements of the university and a college program are very vital in the realization of the institutional drives and mandates. Research by Garcia *et al.* [12] stated that this could serve a mechanism to further enhance and improve the existing practices, policies, programs, and trainings of the institution. There were already studies that sought the stakeholders' level of awareness and acceptability on the organizations' VMGOs [13]–[23]. There are also several researchers that sought the congruence and relevance of their organizations' VMGOs [24]–[27], as well as the extent that these statements are being disseminated [27]–[30].

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the stakeholders' awareness and acceptability on the VMGOs of the university and the teacher education program is not yet conducted locally. It is for these reasons that this study is conceived in order to determine whether or not the different stakeholders have an acceptable level of awareness of the vision and mission of the university and the goals and outcomes of the different academic programs. The current study aimed to assess the stakeholders' awareness and acceptability of the college VMGOs statements. It further sought to compare the level of awareness and acceptability of school personnel, parents/officials, and students and explore the relationship between awareness and acceptability of the statements.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Generally, the study utilized a descriptive method of research to assess for the awareness and acceptance of the VMGOs statements. A correlational analysis was conducted to test the relationship between awareness and acceptance. While a comparative analysis was done to compare the awareness and acceptance scores of school personnel, parents/officials, and students.

2.1. Participants and setting

The location of the study is at Isabela State University, Rang-ayan, Roxas, Isabela, Philippines. The target population is the stakeholders of the college of education during the school year 2020-2021. The college offers Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSE) major in mathematics and major in Filipino. There were three sections of freshmen students (no major), two sections of second year students majoring in Filipino, one section of second year students majoring in mathematics, one section of third year students

majoring in Filipino, and another section of third year students majoring in mathematics. The expected population size consists of 100 school personnel, 300 students, and 300 parents/officials. Hence, the 406 stakeholders who served as respondents in the study (42 school personnel, 106 parents, and 258 students) represent the 58 percent of the population. Of the 406 respondents, 301 (74.1%) were females and 105 (25.9%) were males.

2.2. Instrumentation

A research instrument was developed in the form of rating scales. The levels used for awareness were 1 if not at all aware, 2 if slightly aware, 3 if moderately aware, 4 if very aware, and 5 if extremely aware. The levels used for acceptability were 1 if not at all acceptable, 2 if slightly acceptable, 3 if moderately acceptable, 4 if very acceptable, and 5 if completely acceptable. The content validity of the instrument was established first. The Cronbach reliability of the scales for awareness and acceptability were .991 and .992, respectively. The respondents were asked to rate their awareness and acceptability of 16 statements including one vision, one mission, 5 IO, 2 college goals, and 7 PO.

2.3. Data collection

Due to limitations on personal data gathering brought by the existing protocols against COVID-19, an electronic survey was conducted through the use of a Google Form. The research instrument was tailored in a Google Form and the link was sent to all the target respondents through messenger group chats and Facebook groups. We requested the students to assist their parents (guardians) in answering the survey honestly and completely. Despite this request, however, some parents were not still able to respond to the survey for some unidentified reasons. The researchers informed the respondents about the nature of the current study and assured them that their responses would be kept confidential most especially from the office of the college dean and higher school authorities. This step was done to allow the respondents to freely indicate their real level of awareness and acceptability of the VMGOs.

2.4. Data analysis

The data were transferred to SPSS for data analysis. Frequency count and percent were utilized to gauge the respondents' distribution as to sex and category as stakeholder. Mean was used to determine their average awareness scores and acceptability of the VMGOs. The mean scores were described according to the guidelines as presented in Table 1.

Standard deviations were also computed to gauge how consistent their responses are regarding their awareness and the acceptability of the VMGOs. Pearson correlation was used to explore the relationship between the awareness and acceptability scores. While one-way between-groups analysis of variance was conducted to compare the awareness and acceptability scores indicated by school personnel, parents/officials, and students.

Table 1. Mean score guidelines

Scale	Mean	Awareness	Acceptability
1	0.50–1.49	Not at all aware	Not at all acceptable
2	1.50–2.49	Slightly aware	Slightly acceptable
3	2.50–3.49	Moderately aware	Moderately acceptable
4	3.50–4.49	Very aware	Very acceptable
5	4.50–5.00	Extremely aware	Completely acceptable

3. RESULTS

In the context of institutional development and strategic planning, stakeholders' awareness and acceptance of an educational institution's VMGOs statements play a pivotal role. These statements define the institution's core principles, objectives, and future direction. Understanding stakeholders' perspectives regarding these statements is essential for effective strategic decision-making and alignment of efforts. This analysis delves into the findings presented in Table 2, which shows that the stakeholders indicated they are very aware of the VMGOs statements. Similarly, they rated the VMGOs statements as very acceptable. Such a robust awareness and acceptance of the VMGOs statements can lay a solid foundation for effective strategic planning, informed decision-making, and collaborative efforts within the academic community.

Table 3 shows the comparison of the awareness scores among the categories of stakeholders. The results showed 99% confidence level in claiming that the school personnel were more aware than the parents/officials and students but the students were more aware than the parents/officials. Thereby, the parents/officials were the least aware.

Table 2. Stakeholders' level of awareness and acceptability of the VMGOs

Statements	Awareness			Acceptability		
	M	SD	Description	M	SD	Description
Vision	3.92	1.18	Very aware	4.03	1.09	Highly accepted
Mission	3.91	1.16	Very aware	4.03	1.08	Highly accepted
IO 1	3.73	1.14	Very aware	3.94	1.07	Highly accepted
IO 2	3.69	1.13	Very aware	3.91	1.10	Highly accepted
IO 3	3.77	1.13	Very aware	3.89	1.09	Highly accepted
IO 4	3.73	1.14	Very aware	3.89	1.06	Highly accepted
IO 5	3.86	1.13	Very aware	3.92	1.10	Highly accepted
College goal 1	3.80	1.14	Very aware	3.90	1.11	Highly accepted
College goal 2	3.83	1.13	Very aware	3.92	1.07	Highly accepted
PO 1	3.73	1.16	Very aware	3.87	1.08	Highly accepted
PO 2	3.75	1.13	Very aware	3.88	1.10	Highly accepted
PO 3	3.77	1.15	Very aware	3.82	1.11	Highly accepted
PO 4	3.75	1.16	Very aware	3.86	1.11	Highly accepted
PO 5	3.79	1.16	Very aware	3.92	1.09	Highly accepted
PO 6	3.80	1.15	Very aware	3.90	1.11	Highly accepted
PO 7	3.79	1.15	Very aware	3.93	1.11	Highly accepted

Table 3. Comparison of stakeholders' awareness of the VMGOs

Quality statements	School personnel		Parents/officials		Students		F (2, 403)
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	
Vision	4.70 ^a	.55	3.01 ^c	1.28	4.17 ^b	.99	58.74 ^{**}
Mission	4.60 ^a	.70	3.07 ^c	1.24	4.15 ^b	.99	50.50 ^{**}
IO 1	4.48 ^a	.71	2.95 ^c	1.23	3.93 ^b	.99	45.87 ^{**}
IO 2	4.51 ^a	.67	3.00 ^c	1.24	3.85 ^b	1.00	38.58 ^{**}
IO 3	4.63 ^a	.66	3.11 ^c	1.25	3.91 ^b	.99	37.65 ^{**}
IO 4	4.48 ^a	.77	3.00 ^c	1.22	3.92 ^b	1.00	41.08 ^{**}
IO 5	4.60 ^a	.70	3.16 ^c	1.27	4.03 ^b	.99	37.08 ^{**}
College goal 1	4.58 ^a	.63	3.04 ^c	1.25	3.99 ^b	.99	43.88 ^{**}
College goal 2	4.63 ^a	.62	3.12 ^c	1.24	4.01 ^b	.99	41.19 ^{**}
PO 1	4.58 ^a	.66	3.05 ^c	1.27	3.88 ^b	1.03	36.79 ^{**}
PO 2	4.60 ^a	.62	3.09 ^c	1.27	3.88 ^b	.98	37.36 ^{**}
PO 3	4.65 ^a	.61	3.10 ^c	1.25	3.91 ^b	1.03	37.66 ^{**}
PO 4	4.56 ^a	.74	3.11 ^c	1.31	3.89 ^b	1.01	32.32 ^{**}
PO 5	4.63 ^a	.62	3.12 ^c	1.28	3.93 ^b	1.03	35.76 ^{**}
PO 6	4.65 ^a	.61	3.12 ^c	1.28	3.95 ^b	1.01	38.00 ^{**}
PO 7	4.60 ^a	.66	3.14 ^c	1.32	3.93 ^b	1.00	33.40 ^{**}

Note. ** means significant at .01 level

As presented in Table 4, the school personnel consistently registered the highest level of acceptance of the VMGOs. The students reported a greater level of acceptance as compared to the parents/officials. Thereby, the parents/officials were consistently the least accepting group. As shown in Table 5, there was a consistent significant acceptable relationship between awareness and acceptability across all the VMGOs statements. These constructs share a variance ranging from 51% to 61%.

Table 4. Comparison of stakeholders' acceptability of the VMGOs

Quality statements	School personnel		Parents/officials		Students		F (2, 403)
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	
Vision	4.53 ^a	.71	3.49 ^c	1.26	4.18 ^b	.97	21.78 ^{**}
Mission	4.60 ^a	.66	3.50 ^c	1.18	4.15 ^b	1.00	22.46 ^{**}
IO 1	4.56 ^a	.70	3.53 ^c	1.18	4.01 ^b	1.01	16.31 ^{**}
IO 2	4.60 ^a	.62	3.46 ^c	1.23	3.98 ^b	1.02	19.11 ^{**}
IO 3	4.65 ^a	.61	3.45 ^c	1.23	3.95 ^b	1.01	20.56 ^{**}
IO 4	4.60 ^a	.62	3.44 ^c	1.18	3.96 ^b	.99	20.82 ^{**}
IO 5	4.58 ^a	.66	3.53 ^c	1.22	3.98 ^b	1.05	15.37 ^{**}
College goal 1	4.56 ^a	.63	3.47 ^c	1.23	3.98 ^b	1.05	16.86 ^{**}
College goal 2	4.60 ^a	.62	3.54 ^c	1.19	3.97 ^b	1.01	16.51 ^{**}
PO 1	4.60 ^a	.66	3.48 ^c	1.16	3.92 ^b	1.03	18.02 ^{**}
PO 2	4.60 ^a	.62	3.46 ^c	1.18	3.93 ^b	1.06	18.10 ^{**}
PO 3	4.65 ^a	.61	3.39 ^c	1.22	3.87 ^b	1.04	21.69 ^{**}
PO 4	4.58 ^a	.70	3.47 ^c	1.23	3.90 ^b	1.05	16.43 ^{**}
PO 5	4.58 ^a	.66	3.55 ^c	1.25	3.98 ^b	1.02	14.87 ^{**}
PO 6	4.63 ^a	.62	3.54 ^c	1.21	3.93 ^b	1.06	15.67 ^{**}
PO 7	4.65 ^a	.65	3.54 ^c	1.21	3.98 ^b	1.05	16.93 ^{**}

Note. ** means significant at .01 level

Table 5. Relationship between awareness and acceptability of VMGOs

Statements	Awareness		Acceptability		R
	M	SD	M	SD	
Vision	3.92	1.18	4.03	1.09	.783**
Mission	3.91	1.16	4.03	1.08	.777**
IO 1	3.73	1.14	3.94	1.07	.731**
IO 2	3.69	1.13	3.91	1.10	.760**
IO 3	3.77	1.13	3.89	1.09	.779**
IO 4	3.73	1.14	3.89	1.06	.745**
IO 5	3.86	1.13	3.92	1.10	.775**
College goal 1	3.80	1.14	3.90	1.11	.722**
College goal 2	3.83	1.13	3.92	1.07	.715**
PO 1	3.73	1.16	3.87	1.08	.732**
PO 2	3.75	1.13	3.88	1.10	.746**
PO 3	3.77	1.15	3.82	1.11	.761**
PO 4	3.75	1.16	3.86	1.11	.740**
PO 5	3.79	1.16	3.92	1.09	.724**
PO 6	3.80	1.15	3.90	1.11	.731**
PO 7	3.79	1.15	3.93	1.11	.724**

Note. ** means significant at .01 level

4. DISCUSSION

This research explores the stakeholders' awareness and acceptance of the VMGOs of a higher education institution. The stakeholders, as a whole, indicated a high awareness and acceptance of the VMGOs. Several studies also underscore that stakeholders are aware and do accept their university's VMGOs [1], [12], [13], [28], [31]–[35]. This finding implies that stakeholders have extensive information about the VMGO of the university. In the current study, this is a positive sign for the college as it indicates that the stakeholders understand the purpose and objectives of the college. This could lead to higher levels of support for the college and its initiatives, which can ultimately contribute to its success.

The three groups of stakeholders, however, significantly differed in their level of awareness and acceptance. The school personnel specified the highest level of awareness and acceptance [12], [29], [36], [37], while the parents/officials had the lowest [14], [21]. The parents/officials indicated that they were only moderately aware of the VMGOs and they found the vision, some IO, goals, and PO moderately acceptable. This indicates that the college has been more successful in communicating its goals and objectives to the school personnel. It could also suggest that school personnel have a greater level of engagement with the program and its initiatives. On the other hand, the lower level of awareness and acceptance among students and parents/officials could indicate a need for the program to improve its outreach and communication strategies to these groups. Especially, the finding that the parents/officials were the least aware and accepting of the VMGOs suggests that there may be a disconnection between the program and this group of stakeholders. This could result in a lack of support and resources from this group, which could negatively impact the program's success.

Moreover, the stakeholders' awareness and acceptance of the VMGOs were significantly and positively associated [32], [38]. These two variables share an adequate amount of variance ranging from 51% to 61%. This signifies that the more aware the stakeholders are about the VMGOs, the more likely they will accept it. Research by Escolano [36] on the other hand, claimed that there is no significant relationship between the two, as she argued that stakeholders may not fully aware of the VMGO but they truly accept it.

The current findings have important implications for the program in terms of how it communicates and promotes its VMGOs. It may be necessary to improve the college's communication and outreach efforts to parents/officials, who were found to be the least aware and accepting of the VMGOs. This could involve using different communication channels, such as social media, newsletters, or parent/student forums, to provide information about the college's VMGOs and to engage with these groups. It may be beneficial to increase engagement with the school personnel, who were found to be the most aware and accepting of the VMGOs. This could involve engaging school personnel in program initiatives and events, or providing opportunities for them to provide feedback and input into the college's VMGOs. Additionally, the college should evaluate its current communication and outreach strategies to determine their effectiveness in raising awareness and acceptance of the VMGOs among all stakeholders. Based on this evaluation, the program may need to make changes to its strategies in order to improve communication and engagement with students, parents/officials, and other stakeholders.

The university should intensify widest dissemination of its VMGOs in a form of print such as tarpaulin, pamphlets, flyers, and leaflets. With the advent of advance technology, the university should also consider uploading videos and movie clips in various social media. Conducting stakeholders' meeting that will regularly orient them with the VMGOs of the university may also be taken into consideration.

Mandatory posting of VMGO in all strategic places such as adopted barangays, linkages, extension partners, and others. Stakeholders should also be informed that the university programs, activities, and undertakings are aligned and in support to its VMGOs. Furthermore, monitoring of stakeholders' awareness and acceptance of the VMGO should be done periodically. This could involve conducting surveys, focus groups, or other forms of engagement to gather feedback and ensure that the college is meeting the needs and expectations of all stakeholders.

5. CONCLUSION

The study highlights that the stakeholders of a teacher education college have different levels of awareness and acceptance of the VMGOs, i.e., the school personnel are the most aware and accepting, followed by the students, while the parents/officials are the least aware and accepting. The awareness and acceptance of these stakeholders are directly related. Therefore, the college has to regularly monitor the stakeholders' awareness and acceptance of the VMGO, use clear and effective communication in raising stakeholders' awareness and acceptance of VMGOs, focus on increasing awareness as a means of increasing acceptance, encourage stakeholders' engagement, and continuously evaluate and adjust its communication strategies. Further, future research may consider focusing on identifying the factors that contribute to the low stakeholders' acceptance and awareness of VMGOs.

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